

**THE CONCEPT AND GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF
HYPERBOLE AS A STYLISTIC DEVICE**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7481884>

Azimova Muhayyo Pulatjonovna
*Teacher of the English language
of the NUUz, Department
of Foreign language and literature*

Annotation: *This article deals with the lexical and syntactic stylistic device hyperbole. In particular, the scientific research works conducted by the world's linguists on this styleme are analyzed and the author's personal views on them are expressed.*

In the scientific literature, one can find many interpretations of such a technique as hyperbole (from the Greek hyperbole - excess, exaggeration). According to E.V. Polikarpova “the essence of such a non-elementary phenomenon as a hyperbole cannot be covered by one exhaustive definition” [12, p. 82]. A variety of definitions of this technique can be grouped depending on the generic concept that they indicate.

Yu.I. Borisenko distinguishes 4 groups of interpretations of hyperbole:

1. Hyperbole as a technique.
2. Hyperbole as a means of creating figurativeness, expressiveness, figurativeness.
3. Hyperbole as a figure of speech.
4. Hyperbole as a trope [5, p.111].

A technique is understood as a method in the implementation of something. M.T. Sultanova classifies hyperbole as a rhetorical device that implements “a

pragmatically motivated and modeled deviation from the norm or its neutral variant carried out in speech in order to have a certain impact on the addressee” [27, p. 182].

According to Y.I. Borisenko, hyperbole acts as a stylistic device, i.e. a deviation from the linguistic and speech norm, but not from the point of view of the mechanism of its construction, but from the point of view of its functional purpose: hyperbole serves as a means of designing genres of certain functional styles or implementing a stylistic task in a particular text, a means of the writer's individual style [5, p. 113]

I.R. Galperin argues that hyperbole is a stylistic device of exaggeration, which, from the point of view of the real possibilities for the realization of a thought, is doubtful or simply unbelievable [7, p. 152]. The writer who uses this artistic technique counts on the understanding of the reader. Hyperbole is an agreement between a writer and a reader and is a means of the most vivid, colorful, figurative and expressive description of objects and phenomena.

Among the stylistic devices, tropes and non-tropical (figurative and non-figurative) formations are distinguished. The opinions of researchers about whether the hyperbole is a trope or a figure of speech are divided. Under the path it is necessary to understand the words and phrases with the help of which this or that object is named in such a way that its associative-figurative connections with another object are indicated. Figures of speech, on the other hand, act as fragments of a text sentence, drawing attention to one or another component of the statement due to the peculiarities of their syntactic organization [7, p. 27].

T.Kh. Khazagerov notes that hyperbole also acts as a trope, namely a kind of metaphor, the characteristic of which is the presence of a juxtaposing, and the juxtaposed is only implied in this case, and a figure, for which the presence of both the juxtaposed and juxtaposing components is mandatory [15, p. 218]. A frequent principle for the formation of a hyperbole is the principle of transfer, which is understood as an explicit or implicit comparison of objects, and as a result of

which the property of another is attributed to only one object. This aspect brings hyperbole closer to metaphor.

According to V.V. Gurevich hyperbole is a figurative expression that consists in exaggerating the strength, size, beauty, and meaning of what is being described. The basis of the hyperbole is the deviation from the objective quantitative assessment of the subject of the phenomenon and quality [12, p. 142].

The use of hyperbole allows the authors to give thoughts an unusual form, and the text - a bright emotional coloring, persuasiveness. In hyperbole there is a clash between the ordinary, the everyday and the unimaginable, the grotesque, the unreal. In hyperbole, the realization of two meanings of the word takes place - the main, subject-logical and contextual-emotional. It can be expressed by linguistic units of different levels, for example, a word, a phrase, a sentence.

Thus, we can conclude that despite the multifaceted interpretation of the concept of hyperbole, its main feature is exaggeration, which is used to create brightness, dynamism of the description, and attract the reader's attention.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Avanesova, N.V. Emotionality and expressiveness - categories of communicative linguistics / N.V. Avanesova // Bulletin of the Yugorsk State University. - 2010. - No. 2. - P. 5-9.
2. Arnold, I.V. Stylistics. Modern English: textbook. for universities / I. V. Arnold. – M.: Flinta, 2006. – 384 p.
3. Akhmanova, O. S. Dictionary of linguistic terms /O. S. Akhmanova. - M.: Editorial URSS, 2004. - 571 p.
4. Bloch M. Ya. Intensity as an artistic technique /M. Ya. Bloch // Bulletin of the Bryansk state. university - 2017. - No. 3. – S. 237-242.

5. Borisenko, Yu. I. On the linguistic status of hyperbole and the mechanism of its formation / Yu. I. Borisenko // Humanitarian and social sciences. - 2010 - No. 5 - P. 111 - 115.
6. Vlasova, E. V. Hyperbolic metaphor in English speech (based on the novel "Past Secrets" by K. Kelly) / E. V. Vlasova // Almanac of modern science and education. - Tambov: Diploma, 2015. - No. 7. - S. 44-47.
7. Galperin, I. R. Stylistics of the English language: textbook. allowance / I. R. Galperin - M.: Higher School, 1981. - 334 p.
8. Gurevich, V. V. English Stylistics: Stylistics of the English language /V. V. Gurevich. - M.: Flinta: Nauka, 2011. - 72 p.
9. Dorogova, T. A. Interaction of hyperbole, meiosis and litotes /T.A. Dorogova // Bulletin of the Moscow State University. university - 2011. - No. 6. - S. 106 - 110.
10. Krysin, L.P. Hyperbole in Russian colloquial speech: textbook. allowance / L. P. Krysin. - M.: Languages of Slavic culture, 2004. -262 p.
11. Leskina, S. V. Language specifics of hyperbolization of journalistic texts in Russian and English / S. V. Leskina, V. B. Sharonova // Bulletin of the South Ural State University. university - 2017. - No. 1. - S. 31-34.
- 12.12 Polikarpova, E. V. Hyperbole in modern German (lexicological aspect): author. dis. ... cand. philol. Sciences / E. V. Polikarpova. - M.: Mosk. state ped. in-t im. V. I. Lenin, 1990. - 16 p.
13. Sultanova, M. T. Cognitive Aspect of Linguistic and Speech Hyperbole (Based on the Works of the Magic Realism Genre) /M. T. Sultanova // Philological Sciences. - 2010. - No. 2. – pp. 50-57
14. Tikhomirov, S. A. Hyperbole in the gradual aspect: author. dis. ... cand. philol. Sciences / S.A. Tikhomirov. - Moscow, 2006. - 21 p.
15. Khazagerov T. G. General rhetoric: a course of lectures; dictionary of rhetorical devices / T. G. Khazagerov, V. P. Shirin. - Rostov n / D, 1999. - 218 p.